

THE VIABILITY OF THE MOUNTAINOUS REGION IN NORTHEASTERN ROMANIA IS SUPPORTED BY THE SECTORS OF WHOLESALE AND RETAIL TRADE, AS WELL AS THE REPAIR OF MOTOR VEHICLES AND MOTORCYCLES

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Abstract

This paper delineates the active enterprise population within the Wholesale and Retail Trade, as well as the Repair of Motor Vehicles and Motorcycles sector in the North-East region of Romania. The focal rationale behind examining this sector lies in its pivotal role in sustaining the mountainous area. The article employs a statistical analysis, utilizing data sourced from Eurostat and processed through SPSS. The mountainous region is identified as harboring substantial potential, particularly due to the high-quality value of primary products. Consequently, any local and central measures devised should incorporate the insights derived from this study.

Keywords: sustainability of the mountain area; North-East region of Romania; wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles sectors

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1. Introduction

The economic activities conducted by active enterprises in the secondary and tertiary sectors (excluding the agricultural sector) have the potential to serve as the driving force for the development of the North-East region of Romania. The abundance of active enterprises, coupled with their emphasis on quality and added value to the local economy, contributes to an elevation in the standard of living and overall well-being of the population. In light of this, governmental initiatives are deemed necessary, with a particular emphasis on local efforts, to foster entrepreneurial development (Benaki, 2007; Ucellini, 2010).

To assess the outlined scenario concerning the active enterprise population, the paper formulated the following hypotheses:

1. Alternative Hypothesis H1: The likelihood of a downturn in the specified sectors is positively associated with the prevailing trends in these sectors. Specifically, this correlation is observed in sectors where there is an intensification of activity, with a frequency greater than or equal to 1.5.
2. To substantiate the second hypothesis, the null hypothesis H0 posits: The probability of recession in the listed sectors is negatively correlated with the central trends in these sectors. This correlation is evident in sectors where there is a de-intensification of activity, with a frequency less than 1.5 (Blažková et al., 2016).

2. Results and data

Statistical data pertaining to the dynamics of the Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Motor Vehicles and Motorcycles sector (depicted in Figures 1, 2, 3, and 4) reveals a predominantly average value of 32,022.13, accompanied by a standard error of 2,733,544. The 95% confidence interval spans from 25,558.32 to 38,485.93, with a lower 5% average value of 32,147.19, a median value of 32,335.00, a variance of 59,778,113,268, and a standard deviation of 7,731.631. The minimum and maximum values are 21,448 in 2008 and 40,345 in 2015, respectively. The interval is 18,897, the interquartile range is 15,896, and the gap is -159, accompanied by a standard error of 0.752. The Kurtosis is -1.838, with a standard error of 1.481.

Upon initial analysis, the distribution curve appears relatively symmetrically centered, with scores tightly concentrated around the average, exhibiting leptokurtic characteristics despite being unimodal. The working hypothesis posits that the score distribution is normal, thereby warranting the application of parametric tests. Although extreme values are limited in number, they induce a positive asymmetry and exert a clinically significant impact on the histogram appearance. The concentration of numerous scores around the average ($M = 32,022.13$) introduces a degree of leptokurtosis, influenced by phenomena within the Romanian economy. Applying the logarithm to the obtained values, in accordance with universally accepted statistical principles, serves to balance the distribution towards the normal Gauss-Laplace curve.

The normal Q-Q plot test, post-logarithm, illustrates a distribution of actual scores aligning with normal values, represented by the diagonal line on the graph—a characteristic of a normal distribution. Figure 2's Q-Q detrended plot test, examining the dispersion of empirical scores against normal values after logarithmic transformation, indicates that they fall within one standard deviation, indicative of a normal distribution.

Through logarithmic transformation, the scores underwent statistical processing, accounting for all pertinent factors to yield data closely reflective of the recorded reality in the North-East region of Romania, even considering the temporary distributional imbalances induced by economic measures.

Figure 1 presents a histogram visualizing the Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Motor Vehicles and Motorcycles sector.

Source: Author processing according to Eurostat data - Business Demography Statistics

Figure 2. Distribution chart of normal Q-Q plot for Wholesale and Retail; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles by logarithm

Source: Author processing according to Eurostat data - Business Demography Statistics

The significance of the examination conducted in Figures 3 and 4 lies in the imperative to meticulously scrutinize the impacts of specific factors on the progression of wholesale and retail trade, as well as the repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles.

Figure 3. Dispersion of the scores observed, compared to normal, by the Q-Q detrended plot test, after logarithm

Source: Author processing according to Eurostat data - Business Demography Statistics

Subsequent to the implementation of normality assessments subsequent to logarithmic transformation, it becomes imperative to repudiate the null hypothesis, paving the way for a thorough examination of the working hypothesis. This necessitates a meticulous scrutiny of the proposed working hypothesis given the observed deviations from the expected normal distribution.

Figure 4. Inter-court diagram for Wholesale and Retail; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles

Source: Author processing according to Eurostat data - Business Demography Statistics

Conducting both descriptive and inferential analyses entail an examination of the score distribution conforming to normalcy assumptions as posited by the working hypothesis. The application of parametric tests is thereby warranted to assess the statistical significance and validity of the hypothesized normal distribution of scores.

3. Conclusion

Throughout the scrutinized timeframe, the central tendency within the examined sector, represented by an average of 32,022.13, signifies a noteworthy escalation in the active enterprise population in the North-East

region. The demographic surge is evident, with the count rising from 26,045 in 2008 to 39,925 in 2015. The verification of Hypothesis H1, denoting activity intensification, substantiates a total frequency variation of 1.8, oscillating between 0.5 and 2.3.

The statistical data and the presented histogram collectively affirm the pronounced concentration and developmental trajectory characterizing this sector in the northeastern region of Romania. Furthermore, the statistical insights corroborate an accentuated growth rate within this sector, aligning with previous research findings (Covaci B., 2018 & 2019; Covaci M., 2009, 2014, 2017, 2019).

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